

THE GLOBAL PARTNERSHIP FOR EDUCATION KNOWLEDGE AND INNOVATION EXCHANGE (KIX)

110508-001: Scaling Inclusive Early Learning with Deaf Children 1st Annual Interim Report, January – July 2025

Kenya, Rwanda, and Malawi

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Acronyms

CF:	Community Facilitator
DA:	Discourse analysis
DOI:	Digital Object Identifier
DSNE	Directorate of Special Needs Education
DTF:	Disability Trust Fund
ECCE:	Early Childhood Care and Education
ECD:	Early Childhood Development
G1:	Grade 1
G2:	Grade 2
GBV:	Gender based violence
GEI:	Gender Equality and Inclusion
GESI:	Gender Equality and Social Inclusion
GPE:	Global Partnership for Education
IDRC:	International Development Research Centre
ICED:	International Congress on the Education of the Deaf
IEPA:	Africa East Inclusive Education Policy Academy
KICD	Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development
KISE:	Kenya Institute of Special Education
KIX:	Knowledge and Innovation
KNAD:	Kenya National Association of the Deaf
KOL:	Kentalis Observation List
KSL:	Kenya Sign Language
MANAD	Malawi National Association for the Deaf
MEL:	Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning
MoE	Ministry of Education
MSL:	Malawi Sign Language
NCST:	National Council of Science and Technology
PAW:	Parents Awareness Workshop
PP1:	Pre-primary 1
PP2:	Pre-primary 2
PTA:	Parent Teacher Association
RAC:	Research Advisory Committee
ROSIE:	Research on Scaling the Impact of Innovations in Education
RSL:	Rwanda Sign Language
RSLA:	Research Sign Language Assessment
SL:	Sign Language
SRHR:	Sexual Reproductive Health Rights
TPD:	Teacher Professional Development
TSC	Teachers Service Commission
UDL:	Universal Design for Learning
WCAG:	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WFD:	World Federation of the Deaf

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- **Executive Summary**

The Scaling Inclusive Early Learning with Deaf Children project focuses on generating knowledge and evidence to scale inclusive, equitable, and quality ECCE. The goal is to ensure Deaf children are not left behind in foundational linguistic, cognitive, and social-emotional development, and that they have a smooth transition to school. This is achieved by creating a sign language-rich environment in schools and at home. The innovation is composed of five pillars, including: Deaf teachers fluent in the local sign language ; accessible teaching and learning materials in local sign language ; support to empower teachers with the knowledge and skills to effectively teach and assess Deaf learners ; an evidence-based sign language acquisition assessment to measure learning gains ; and an experimental final component that involves engaging families and communities to support their Deaf children's language learning journey outside of school.

Over the 6-month period (January 2025 – June 2025), the project team has implemented activities tailored to the key objectives of the research. Below are activities achieved by country:

- **Kenya:** The project in Kenya kicked off with stakeholder engagement in April. The Kenya Research Advisory Committee (RAC) was also formed to provide technical support for the project and ensure the contextualization of the activities. In May, trained parents of Deaf children, who became community facilitators, conducted subsequent Parents Awareness Workshops (PAW) at St. Anthony School for the Deaf in Webuye. In June, the Kenya project team joined the Malawi project team for master trainer training on the Research Sign Language Assessment tool (RSLA), which was supported by Kentalis. The training also included a review of the tool for contextualization and piloting with Deaf children in PP1, PP2, G1, and G2.
- **Rwanda:** The first Research Advisory Committee (RAC) meeting was held in Rwanda in February to introduce the committee to the project and review the work plan. Meetings were also held with the Rwanda Education Board's (REB) Deputy Director General to inform the institution of the project's objectives and to understand how the generated knowledge will contribute to the country's education priorities. A Parents Awareness Workshop (PAW) was conducted in March, which included headteachers from the schools selected for the project. The project team in Rwanda met with other KIX grantees, an opportunity organised by the visiting IDRC officer, Patrick Walugembe. In preparation for the intervention activities, six Deaf teacher assistants who will be deployed in treatment schools were identified and recruited. In May, the Kentalis team trained master trainers, including the Deaf teacher assistants, on how to administer the RSLA, and then piloted the tool in one of the schools with eight Deaf learners.
- **Malawi:** In January, the Malawi team obtained their research authorisation from the National Council of Science and Technology (NCST), enabling the commencement of project activities. Early on in the project, Deaf teacher assistants who would support the work in treatment schools were identified and recruited. Additionally, a MEL manager was also recruited to bridge the gap for the staff who transitioned. The Research Advisory Committee (RAC) was also set up to support project activities and provide guidance for contextualisation. A project launch and stakeholder engagement were conducted in May alongside the PAW. In preparation for the baseline assessment, training of master trainers on the RSLA was conducted by the Kentalis team and the tool was piloted in one of the Deaf schools.

In connection with the project's first objective, **generating knowledge and evidence**, the team finalised a situational analysis across the three countries. The report provided an overview of the policy and

implementation environment, discussing cross-country similarities and differences. It also mapped out existing initiatives and stakeholders that support Deaf education and analysed gender disparities.

A key part of this project is to measure the impact of our innovation in creating sign language-rich learning environments. Baseline and endline assessments will be conducted in treatment and control schools in Kenya, Rwanda, and Malawi to generate evidence of impact and learning for scaling. Learning outcomes will be assessed using the RSLA. During this period, the RSLA tools were developed, reviewed, and contextualised for each country, before being scaled to Rwanda and Malawi. Training of master trainers on how to administer these tools for the baseline was conducted in both Rwanda and Malawi. Furthermore, training was provided to the Deaf teachers who would be assessing learners in the schools. The tools were piloted in a Deaf school in Rwanda in May and another in Malawi in June. The Kenyan team joined the Malawi team for during the training and provided support during the pilot study.

On the second objective of **strengthening the capacity** of ECCE institutions and parents/caregivers of Deaf learners, the consortium scaled the Parent Awareness Workshops in Rwanda and Malawi in March and May, respectively. The workshops aimed to showcase Deaf role models through the involvement of Deaf teacher assistants, increase awareness and empower parents on how to support Deaf children, and build the capacity of parents as community facilitators. As part of the scaling approach, the training manuals were to meet the needs of parents across the different contexts. Workshops were conducted in Kinyarwanda in Rwanda and in Chichewa in Malawi to ensure full participation. In Kenya, PAW sessions were conducted using a mix of English and Kiswahili. To ensure the sustainability of the parent peer support groups and community facilitators, Deaf teachers, headteachers, and Early Childhood Development (ECD) coordinators were engaged in the PAW, along with government representatives, to ensure the uptake and continuation of the initiatives.

In Rwanda, the Parents' Awareness Workshop (PAW) was conducted over three days with a total of 30 parents of Deaf children. Headteachers from the selected schools for the Deaf in Rwanda were also part of the PAW to enhance a collaborative approach and support system in awareness creation activities. In Malawi, 33 ECD coordinators from the districts where the project will be carried out and Ministry of Education representatives attended the workshop to enhance the ownership and coordination approach in adopting project activities in national plans. In Kenya, trained community facilitators carried out and facilitated subsequent PAWs in their communities. This was conducted in St. Anthony School for the Deaf in Webuye, and 58 parents attended.

In line with the third objective of **knowledge and evidence mobilisation**, the project team attended the World Bank Conference on *Strengthening Inclusive Education Systems* Regional Learning Exchange through the Africa East Inclusive Education Policy Academy (IEPA). The team shared the project's focus and the importance of accessible materials and assistive technology in supporting the learning journey of children with disabilities. The consortium also attended the Africa Childcare Forum, which was held in Kigali in May. Two event blogs were developed and shared on the IDRC news page to highlight key activities.

A critical gap was identified in the publication of information on the status, progress, achievements, and gaps in deaf education on the African continent. To address this, the project developed the Evidence Library. The [Evidence Library](#) is a website that consolidates the project's original research, as well as final, approved knowledge products developed and approved under this grant. It also features articles, publications, and Digital Object Identifier (DOI) links to other relevant evidence. Primarily, it serves as a collaborative tool to connect organisations and researchers working on related topics, fostering knowledge sharing and cross-institutional engagement. It also provides authoritative resources, for allies and advocates of Deaf people and changemakers in Deaf education.

Key learnings:

1. **Understanding the context is crucial for effectively scaling and documenting impact.** The project is scaling differently and taking different pathways depending on the context of each country. The recognition of sign language (SL) as a language of instruction is critical in ensuring the standardisation of teaching approaches. However, while Kenya Sign Language (KSL) is officially recognised as a language of instruction in Kenya, Rwanda Sign Language (RSL) and Malawi Sign Language (MSL) are not yet official languages of instruction in their respective countries. Official sign language recognition ensures that Deaf children get to learn in a language they can use and understand. Deaf learners first need to gain sign language proficiency to communicate before the connection to letters and words can be made. They also need sign language to communicate their understanding of written text. Thus, the pathway from language acquisition in a sign language (L1) to literacy learning in a second language (L2) requires a stepwise progression—language first, then literacy. In foundational language and literacy learning, clear and distinct parallels exist among the challenges of all linguistic and ethnic minority learners, including Deaf people, who are a significant linguistic minority (WFD, 2016).

Official sign language recognition also opens pathways for Deaf people to become teachers who are fluent in their “mother tongue,” their national sign language. WFD advocates for Deaf individuals to be at the forefront of teaching their national sign languages. They emphasize that Deaf people have a unique expertise and cultural connection to their sign languages, making them the ideal educators. The WFD also highlights the importance of linguistic human rights, particularly the right of Deaf children to learn their sign language as their mother tongue.

Without official recognition of a country’s national sign language, it cannot be accepted as a language of instruction in schools. As a result, Deaf learners have no access to foundational learning and learning materials that are accessible to them. This leads to poor learning outcomes and high dropout rates.

2. **Inclusion and deaf leadership are central to achieving the project's expected outcomes.** There is a scarcity of certified Deaf teachers across all three countries. Through the Digital Story Time project in Kenya funded by iGravity, significant progress has been made in increasing its number of certified teachers in Kenya, with others being absorbed by the government. To address this gap in Rwanda and Malawi and as a pathway to scaling building on the progress achieved in Kenya, the project has appointed Deaf youth teacher assistants. Through this project, advocacy will be done with governments to ensure these assistants can enrol in teacher colleges for certification.
3. **Early parental engagement**, which aims to change attitudes and equip parents as community facilitators, is a key component of the project. Across the three countries, the first activity

implemented has been the parents' awareness workshops (PAW), targeting parents of Deaf children associated with the selected schools. The initial workshops created peer-to-peer groups and facilitated parents to become community facilitators to further train other parents in their respective communities.

Conclusion:

Planned activities for the second half of the year will primarily focus on schools, engaging Deaf children and working with teachers. The academic year in Rwanda and Malawi will start in September, at which time baseline assessments will be conducted to measure the language acquisition and literacy of Deaf learners in both treatment and control schools. In Kenya, the academic year will start in January 2026, and the baseline is anticipated to begin at that time.

Following the initial baseline assessments, the sign language-rich environment package will be implemented in the treatment schools. This package includes teacher professional development activities for teachers in PP1, PP2, G1, and G2 in the treatment schools. Additionally, accessible materials developed in each country will be distributed to treatment schools to support learning. Deaf teacher assistants will be deployed to treatment schools to provide in-classroom support to Deaf children and promote sign language skill development. Ongoing support and periodic training will also be conducted to ensure the effective utilisation of these adapted materials.

Subsequent Parents' Awareness Workshops (PAW) with community facilitators will be conducted at a grassroots level in communities across the three countries. The timeline for these sessions with parents will be developed to align with school open days and Parent-Teacher Association meetings.

- **Project rationale and objectives**

The Scaling Inclusive Early Learning with Deaf Children project in Kenya, Rwanda, and Malawi has maintained its key focus area, which is to scale the sign language-rich environment in different contexts to support language development, learning gains and literacy development of Deaf children in ECD and lower primary. The sign language-rich environment is composed of 5 pillars, as illustrated in the image below:

Figure 1: The intervention package

The lack of proper foundational education for Deaf children is the reality of 34 Million Deaf children in the world, and only 2% receive education in sign language. 95% of Deaf children have their first exposure to sign language when they start school, yet no teaching and learning materials are accessible to them. For Deaf children, this results in low literacy levels affecting their cognitive, social and emotional development, which in turn impacts their academic progress. This challenge is caused by a lack of early access to sign language for Deaf children, aggravated by teachers not being fluent enough to support language acquisition, literacy, and effectively implement the curriculum. Deaf learners' first language is sign language, but schools that serve them often lack the accessible teaching and learning materials needed to support its acquisition. This under-resourcing prevents Deaf children from developing a strong foundation in their first language, which is essential for successfully learning a second language

The innovation at scale in this project, as highlighted in Figure 1 above, addresses the challenges Deaf children face and provides a conducive environment for them to excel in school and acquire sign language skills. Deaf teachers are key in ensuring the children improve their SL skills, access learning content, and also serve as role models to the Deaf children, while accessible learning materials are essential in facilitating bilingual education and enhancing SL skills in Deaf children. Through the intervention package, Deaf teachers will be deployed to schools and trained on how to best support Deaf children in the classes using the Digital Story Time videos and materials. Additionally, teachers will have a Teacher Professional Development manual that will guide them through different topics. To assess the impact of the intervention package, learners will be assessed periodically using the Kentallis Observation List (KOL) and the Research Sign Language Assessment (RSLA) tool. To ensure that learning continues at home, parents of the Deaf learners will be trained as community facilitators, who

in turn will train other parents in their respective communities on a wide range of topics all relating to how best to interact, communicate, engage and help their Deaf child at home.

Hence, the objectives of this research project have remained the same and aim to *generate knowledge and evidence to scale inclusive, equitable, quality ECCE that leaves fewer Deaf children behind in foundational linguistic, cognitive, and social-emotional development, and makes way for a smooth transition to school.*

But specifically, the project focuses on:

1. **Generating knowledge and evidence** in the form of research findings, policy briefs, and papers/presentations co-developed with ministry (education, gender, disability) stakeholders & OPDs on how to scale sign-language-rich environments for Deaf learners in educational settings and at home.
2. **Strengthening the capacity** of ECCE institutions and parents/caregivers of Deaf learners to create sign-language-rich environments and support Deaf children in their language, literacy, and learning journey.
3. **Mobilising knowledge and evidence** to inform, advocate for, and improve both ECCE language of instruction policies and practices in Kenya, Malawi, and Rwanda in relation to their national sign languages as first languages and languages of instruction and improve implementation of sign-language-rich learning environments for Deaf learners.

- **Section 1: Project implementation and management**

Since the start of the Scaling Inclusive Early Learning with Deaf Children project, all planned activities have been on track as indicated in the work plan. However, there were some delays in Malawi in acquiring the research permit from the NCST. The research permit for Malawi was acquired in January 2025. To mitigate the issue of the delays, several activities were carried out in an overlapping manner. This has led to keeping the timeline as anticipated. Below is a summary of the key project activities:

Figure 2. Project Milestones.

According to the milestones listed above, major activities that have been accomplished since January 2025 to date for the overall project are elaborated below. Further progress per country is also highlighted, including key results.

Progress towards objective 1: Generate knowledge and evidence on how to scale sign-language-rich environments for Deaf learners in educational settings and at home.

The project has achieved the following activities under the objective of generating knowledge and evidence:

i. Situational analysis:

A situation analysis of each country's context was conducted to understand the current status of Deaf education across the three countries and establish a starting point for the project. This analysis also helps the project identify scaling pathways that best fit each country's context while implementing our innovation of a sign language-rich environment. Additionally, the analysis highlighted existing initiatives that have been implemented to support Deaf education in the three countries.

The situation analysis report is attached as an annexe to this annual report for reference.

Key findings:

- a. Organisations representing and overseeing the rights of Deaf people are present across the three countries and play a key role in advocating for proper accommodation in the education of Deaf children. Furthermore, they play a key role in pushing for SL recognition as a language of instruction.
- b. **Significant gaps exist in policy, teacher training, and resources:** Despite some progress—such as Kenya’s policy recognition of sign language—none of the countries fully implement inclusive early education for Deaf learners. Challenges include limited teacher proficiency in sign language, underfunded systems, and reliance on inadequately trained caregivers. Moreover, there are limited resources and documentation on Deaf education across the three countries. Relevant projects often fail to widely share their reports, which creates a gap in knowledge for others seeking to learn from and build upon their work.
- c. **Deaf learners remain underserved due to inadequate funding and structural barriers:** All three countries face major resource constraints, with inclusive education heavily dependent on external donor funding. Government allocations for Deaf education are insufficient, affecting the sustainability of support services, assistive technologies, and teacher development.

ii. Cost analysis approach:

Conducting a cost analysis of our innovation is essential in supporting scaling approaches and uptake of our innovation into the education system. We are continuing to refine our strategy, and in that regard, we are exploring how to effectively assess the cost per learning gain of Deaf learners.

In May 2025, we attended a three-day workshop organised by the GPE KIX team. The workshop brought together various KIX projects, some of which had already been completed and others which were ongoing. We gained valuable insights from the workshop, particularly through experiences that were shared by the participants. The themes were as follows:

- Day 1: Adaptation and Contextualisation.
- Day 2: Costing.
- Day 3: Institutionalisation.

Key highlights from the webinar that are enabling us to improve our cost-effectiveness process include:

- The importance of continuously developing and improving the processes and capturing lessons learned throughout the implementation of the project.
- The development of a calculation matrix that demonstrates the scalability of our intervention across all aspects, showing cost per learning gain for Deaf learners.
- Engaging local stakeholders as much as possible and aligning the project results with government priorities, while considering available government resources.
- Recognising that human resources are among the most critical assets for scaling, as well as involving all project team members and not just the finance team in the costing process, is important.

We are in the process of refining our cost analysis approach, and we will be able to share more details in the next report. We are anticipating focusing on two analysis models:

Cost Efficiency – measured as the cost per unit of output

Cost Effectiveness – measured as the cost associated with achieving specific outcomes, assessed by comparing treatment and control groups.

Building on the insights and tools gathered during the recent workshop, we will analyse our intervention using both retrospective and actual costs recorded during the implementation and evaluation period. Our approach emphasises using a fit-for-purpose dataset that accurately represents the cost structure of our innovation and supports evidence-based recommendations for potential scaling and uptake by government and other stakeholders.

Targeted metrics

$$\text{Cost Efficiency} = \frac{C}{B}$$

Where:

- C = Total cost of the intervention
- B = Output measure (e.g., learners reached, teachers trained)

Specific indicators include:

- Cost per learner reached: total cost ÷ number of learners served
- Cost per Deaf teacher trained: total cost ÷ number of Deaf teachers completing training
- Cost per resource distributed: total cost ÷ number of materials (e.g., adapted learning materials) distributed

$$\text{Cost-effectiveness} = \frac{\Delta C}{\Delta G}$$

Where:

- ΔC = Difference in cost between intervention and comparison
- ΔG = Difference in learning gain (impact) between groups

Specific indicator:

- Cost per unit of learning gain: total cost ÷ average learning improvement per learner (e.g., RSLA test scores or equivalent).

This model allows us to quantify the cost required to generate each unit of learning improvement attributable to the intervention, providing a basis for comparing the value for money of our approach versus alternatives.

iii. Gender equality and inclusion integration:

The project centres on gender equality and inclusion, with a priority on Deaf children to ensure equitable opportunities and academic excellence comparable to their hearing peers through the creation of a sign-language-rich environment. This initiative is genuinely inclusive and is led by Deaf colleagues who provide invaluable insights into the specific needs of Deaf children. Out of the five Deaf staff members, three are female and two are male, which directly embodies the "Nothing about us without us" principle of disability inclusion.

Our main focus is ECD centres, and it is evident that the majority of caregivers in these centres are women. While our innovation focuses on increasing the number of female Deaf teachers in early childhood education, in line with the gender distribution in the sector, we remain committed to inclusive opportunities for male Deaf teachers as well. The numbers of Deaf teacher assistants that will be employed through this project across the different countries are highlighted in the Table 1 below. To ensure social inclusion, the ECD centres and schools selected for this project are predominantly located in rural areas, with fewer in urban settings. This will enable the research team to gather evidence on the experiences of rural settings concerning accessibility, resource availability, and other factors such as income and poverty levels, and how they affect enrolment.

For the parents' awareness workshops, which aim to create awareness on the importance of sign language and change attitudes towards Deaf children, the project has ensured equal participation from both fathers and mothers of Deaf children. However, in most of the workshops conducted, mothers have been the dominant participants. This is attributed to cultural and contextual issues, where the care of a child is primarily the mother's responsibility. The situation is often more difficult when a Deaf child is born, as the mother is frequently blamed. These circumstances can lead to family separations due to stigma and misconceptions from close families and communities.

The team has developed a gender audit matrix that sets out our targets and will enable us to measure our performance across different components of our innovation. Table 1 below illustrates the gender audit matrix:

Table 1: Gender equality and inclusion.

	GEI aware -1	GEI sensitive - 2	GEI responsive -3	GEI transformative - 4	Total marks
	Does the rationale of the research include evidence on differentiated roles, experiences, impacts on men, women, boys and girls?	Does research design include analysis of differentiated roles, experiences of men, women, boys, and girls?	Research use analysis to implement actions to address, build on, and respond to the findings?	Does the research go beyond the differentiated roles, experiences, perception gaps, and explore underlying structural causes, norms, power relations that cause these differences? Any action being taken to address these causes?	

Participants					
Teachers (female vs male)	1	2	3	4	10
Deaf learners (female vs male)	1	2	3	4	10
Parents (female vs male)	1	2	3	4	10
Stakeholders	1	2	3	4	10
Innovation package					
Deaf teacher assistants	1	2	3	4	10
DST materials	1	2	0	0	3
Teacher professional development	1	2	3	0	6
Parents awareness workshop	1	2	3	4	10

Using the matrix in Table 1, the project highlights its progress in ensuring the overall design is focused on gender equality and is successfully transforming the system.

The project's approach of recruiting Deaf teacher assistants ensures that the majority of those employed are female Deaf teachers. This strategy empowers Deaf teachers, increases their agency, and advocates for their employment. All project activities are Deaf-led. This includes training sessions for PAW, where Deaf team members serve as role models and emphasise the importance of Deaf education. Deaf colleagues will also be involved in data collection at the schools. We have also integrated Sexual Reproductive Health Rights (SRHR) and Gender-Based Violence (GBV) topics into PAW and TPD manuals, which was prompted by our interaction with the Federation of Deaf Women Empowerment Network (FEDWEN) and other similar organisations. These interactions revealed the abuse that Deaf children often face both at home and school. Developing the capacity and raising awareness among the stakeholders surrounding Deaf children will help ensure these issues are appropriately addressed and that proper referral pathways are followed.

iv. School identification and selection/adjustment:

Table 2: School identification and scaling targets.

Country	Schools	Deaf Teacher Assistant	Deaf learners	Parents and Community
Kenya	15	10	>1200	>1200
Rwanda	8	5	>250	>250
Malawi	11	7	>200	>230

The numbers in Table 2 above describe the targeted reach in the three countries across both treatment and control schools. Training will be provided to more teachers than the numbers listed, as existing educators in the selected schools will be trained alongside the Deaf teacher assistants deployed in the treatment schools. For the learners listed, they will be assigned to either the treatment or control group across the four grades that the project is focusing on (PP1, PP2, Grade 1 and Grade 2). Initially, the project focused exclusively on special and inclusive schools. Following consultation with the Ministry of Education in Malawi, however, the project expanded its scope to also include mainstream schools that accommodate Deaf children.

Additionally, the project in Malawi will leverage existing services and partnerships with the Ministry of Health, such as making referrals for diagnosis of hearing loss, to improve early screening and identification. Once Deaf children are screened and certified, they will be referred to the project schools for further support. This will be done in coordination with the Area 25 clinic located in Lilongwe, Malawi. Below is a categorisation of the schools identified in each country:

- **Kenya:** 10 treatment, 5 control, all special schools and government schools, all in rural areas.
- **Rwanda:** 5 treatment, 3 control, special and inclusive schools, government-aided and private, one in urban and others in rural areas.
- **Malawi:** 6 treatment, 5 control among the 11 schools for the project, 5 are special schools and government aided (missionary with support from government for special schools) 6 mainstream schools that are government schools. All the schools are in rural areas, except one, which is in a peri-urban area.

Table 3: List of selected schools per country.

No.	Country	District/County	Name of school/CBCC	Type of School
1	Malawi	Dedza	Mua School for the Deaf	Special School
2		Thyolo	Mountain View School for the Deaf	Special School
3		Chiradzulu	Mary View School for the Deaf	Special School
4		Karonga	Karonga School for the Deaf	Special School
5		Mzimba	Embangweni School for the Deaf	Special School
6		Mchinji	Chimwemwe CBCC	ECD centre
7		Mchinji	Senama CBCC	ECD centre
8		Lilongwe	Grace Foundation CBCC	ECD centre
9		Lilongwe	Umodzi CBCC	ECD centre
10		Nsanje	Chikhawo CBCC	ECD centre
11		Rumphu	Mwankhunukira CBCC	ECD centre
12	Kenya	Garissa	Garissa School for the Deaf	Special School

13		Kilifi	Kibarani School for the Deaf	Special School
14		Murang'a	Murang'a School for the Deaf	Special School
15		Kisumu	Maseno School for the Deaf	Special School
16		Kericho	St. Kizito School for the Deaf-Litein	Special School
17		Nandi	Kapsabet School for the Deaf	Special School
18		Siaya	Sega School for the Deaf	Special School
19		Embu	St. Luke School for the Deaf	Special School
20		Tana River	Lisa Hola School for the Deaf	Special School
21		Homa Bay	Nyangweso School for the Deaf	Special School
22		Nyandarua	Nyandarua School for the Deaf	Special School
23		Kwale	Kinango School for the Deaf	Special School
24		Makueni	Kakuswi School for the Deaf	Special School
25		Siaya	Nina School for the Deaf	Special School
26		Migori	B.L. Tezza Special School for the Deaf	Special School
27	Rwanda	Nyarugenge	GS Institut Filippo Smaldone	Inclusive School
28		Nyagatare	Umutara Deaf School	Special School
29		Huye	Centre de Jeune Sourd et Muet	Inclusive School
30		Nyabihu	Nyabihu school for the deaf	Special School
31		Rubavu	Ubumwe Community Centre	Special School
32		Nyanza	HVP Gatagara	Inclusive School
33		Rutsiro	Centre Komera	Inclusive School
34		Nyamasheke	Centre Alivera	Special School

v. Discourse analysis

As a team committed to reflective practice and continuous learning, we are intentionally examining our ways of working to strengthen the quality and inclusiveness of our programming. To support this, we have adopted discourse analysis (DA) as a methodology for reviewing how we communicate and make decisions that directly affect project implementation. Specifically, we are analysing transcripts from internal and external team meetings held during Year 1 of the project, and using DA to identify patterns in how we talk about Deaf education, inclusion, planning, and accountability. This process helps us to examine whether our internal discourse supports or inadvertently undermines our commitment to equitable, high-quality education for Deaf learners. Through this, we aim to continuously improve our planning, collaboration, and activity delivery.

vi. Scaling strategy:

The project will continually review and refine its scaling strategy to achieve enhanced outcomes. This strategy outlines how to expand the sign language-rich environment for Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) for Deaf learners across Kenya, Rwanda, and Malawi. By providing Deaf children with access to local sign language, inclusive pedagogy, and community support, the strategy aims to close significant language deprivation gaps and build a strong foundation in their language, cognition, and social-emotional skills.

The strategy focuses on three interconnected pillars:

1. Localising the Research Sign Language Assessment Test (RSLA) and teaching materials.
2. Deployment of Deaf teacher assistants who are fluent in sign language.
3. Community engagement through parents who participated in Parents Awareness Workshops (PAW)

The scaling targets are detailed in Table 2: School identification and scaling targets.

Scaling components and approach

The scaling strategy is anchored on three mutually reinforcing components:

1. Localisation of RSLA

Localising the assessment tools is critical to ensure that these tools are valid, accessible, and contextually relevant to the Deaf learners across all three countries: Kenya, Rwanda and Malawi. The process involved translating the tool to each country's sign language, that is, Kenya Sign Language (KSL), Rwanda Sign Language (RSL), and Malawi Sign Language (MSL) and working with Deaf teachers to pilot the tools.

2. Deployment of Deaf assistant teachers

Deaf teachers (who are proficient in their local sign language) will be deployed to treatment schools; this deployment is central to creating a sign-language-rich environment. The presence of these teachers will address the shortage of sign-language-proficient teachers in ECCE; hence, their integration will contribute significantly to the Deaf learners' progress and success.

3. Community engagement through PAW

The third strategy will emphasise community engagement through parents who attended the PAW and became community facilitators. This is to create awareness and support families of Deaf children with the aim of breaking down stigma, strengthening early sign language communication at home, and equipping parents or caregivers with practical tools and skills to support their Deaf children while at home. Parents who have emerged as champions from the PAW sessions will play an important role in mobilising community support and sustaining awareness.

Pathway to scale and Sustainability

This scaling strategy will take a phased and adaptive approach to scale the intervention across the three countries. This approach will include built-in learning loops.

- Phase One: Localisation of RSLA, pilot training of RSLA, Parents Awareness Workshop for community engagement and conducting baseline assessment.
- Phase Two: Strengthen implementation of the intervention through providing necessary support, like refining the tools and training, and conducting baseline and endline assessments.
- Phase Three: Expand the intervention to additional schools across the three countries (as funding allows), and embed the intervention into national ECCE frameworks in all three countries.

To ensure the sustainability and long-term impact of the intervention, the research team is engaging the government (Ministry of Education - MOE) in all three countries at every stage of implementation. Through continuous collaboration with MoE, Organisations of Persons with Disabilities (OPDs) and the

formation of research advisory committees (RACs) in each country, the intervention builds a system of feedback loops that will inform both practice and policy.

A critical part of supporting a system-wide adoption of the intervention will be a rigorous measurement of the intervention's **cost-effectiveness**. As mentioned in the cost analysis section, the research team is continuing to review and improve the cost-effectiveness process. Country-specific data and evidence will be collected and shared with MoE to inform policy, planning, and budgeting. The evidence will be paired with accessible policy briefs and joint presentations to support policy advocacy efforts. The ultimate goal of this research is not only to demonstrate how the intervention works, but also to show that it is practical and scalable with existing systems.

Progress towards objective 2: Strengthen the capacity of ECCE institutions and parents/caregivers of Deaf learners to create sign-language-rich environments and support Deaf children in their language, literacy, and learning journey.

The objective of capacity strengthening involved various training workshops with different stakeholders, including parents, teachers, and government officials.

i. Parents' Awareness Workshops

The main activity that this project initiated was the parents' awareness workshops for parents of Deaf children in the three countries. The objective of the parents' awareness workshop (PAW) is to first understand the issues that parents and families face in having a Deaf child, the stigma faced from the communities, and misconceptions about the abilities of Deaf children that, in turn, limit their access to basic needs and education. The targeted parents are also provided with skills to become community facilitators (CFs) so that they can also go into their communities and reach other parents of Deaf children and change the mindset around deafness and Deaf education. The PAW manual focuses on breaking misconceptions towards deafness and training parents on how to understand it, its causes, and ways to support and communicate with their Deaf child.

The PAW training materials were developed by Kentalis from their over 100 years of experience in Deaf education. These materials include a calendar that summarises the manual content for the CF and uses visualisations to ease understanding and learning for audiences from diverse educational backgrounds. The calendars were given to the CF to use in subsequent training. The other document used was the CF manual, which provided content for each topic, the guidance and approach to use for a participatory and engaging session with parents. These documents were reviewed for contextualization and revision, where appropriate illustrations and pictures were used to reflect the local context. These materials were then translated into the local language for Rwanda and Malawi.

These manuals are attached as an annexe to this report.

Key results:

Across the three countries, parents engaged in brief interviews both before and after the workshops. These sessions served to document their baseline understanding of deafness causation, their level of sign language proficiency, their methods of communication with their Deaf children, their stated learning interests, and the degree to which the workshops addressed their initial expectations. While the workshops weren't expected to have an immediate impact, at the end of the sessions, parents showed a

slight improvement in their understanding of the causes of deafness and the myths surrounding it.

In Rwanda, for instance, 13 out of 16 parents had reported sickness as a cause of deafness before the workshop. At the end of the workshop, all 16 reported sickness as a cause of deafness, which was accurate as per the sessions held. Genetic factors, another cause of deafness, had been reported by only 9 parents pre-workshop, but were reported by 11 post-workshop. In Malawi, pre-workshop, 2 parents reported that deafness was a result of punishment from God, which is a myth, but after the workshop, only 1 parent still reported deafness being a punishment from God.

Additionally, peer support groups were created during the workshops, and subsequent meetings were planned. One of the sessions of the PAW included the parents learning basic sign language, i.e. greetings, names and the alphabet, and this is to continue through the facilitation of the CFs and through the peer support groups. The number of CFs trained in each country is as follows in Table 4 below, with Malawi having the highest number at 35.

Table 4: Number of Community Facilitators trained per Country

	Period	Male	Female	Total
Kenya	November 2024	13	18	31
Rwanda	March 2025	15	13	28
Malawi	May 2025	9	26	35

- In **Kenya**, subsequent workshops led by the trained community facilitators have taken place in different targeted schools. Through the WhatsApp group created for continued support, evidence of different self-initiated actions from the parents trained has been documented. Some parents have enrolled in KSL classes at the Kenya Institute of Special Education (KISE). During the mid-term break in February, up to 308 parents were trained in seven different institutions, with parents inducting others in their schools. The schools included Kuja, Kambui, Kaaga, and Tumutumu schools for the Deaf. Others were St Anthony, Kedowa and Ngala schools for the Deaf. Parents at the latter two schools also received further induction during the April holiday. An outcome case report from the PAW is attached as an annexe that elaborates on the results documented so far.
- In **Rwanda**, an initial PAW was conducted in March with selected parents from the identified schools. 2 parents were selected to participate in a 3-day workshop to build their capacity as community facilitators. Following this workshop, engagement with parents at the community level was carried out in May during the Umuganda literacy activity held in one of the intervention schools in East province, called Umutara Schools for the Deaf. The activity involved Deaf children from the schools reading storybooks to the rest of the community and signing. This event created awareness of the ability of Deaf children and the importance of RSL as a language for communication. The Umuganda literacy event was attended by over 600 children, parents, teachers, school leaders, and members of the local authorities.
- In May, a three-day PAW was held in **Malawi** with parents from the schools involved in the project. This workshop served as the initial capacity building for these parents, preparing them to act as community facilitators.

ii. Accessible learning materials adaptation and contextualisation:

Each country is in the process of developing and making accessible supplementary readers for the different grades. Ultimately, each country targets to use and distribute 100 accessible digital titles to our intervention schools. These materials are based on thematic areas of foundational learning. The materials being developed are in addition to an existing package that was previously developed to support learners with disabilities.

In this project, we are distributing leveraged materials and new materials. The leveraged materials were produced in prior projects. In Rwanda, the accessible learning materials being leveraged were from the Soma Umenye USAID, All Children Reading: a Grand Challenge for Development. In Malawi, we are leveraging materials developed through the Begin with Books project by All Children Reading: A Grand Challenge for Development and from the Disability Trust Fund (DTF) projects. The new titles currently being adapted are from other partners as well as the Ministry of Gender, Community Development and Social Welfare (MoGCDSW). In Kenya, the materials are being adapted from various sources. Other available titles were developed under the DST project.

The table below highlights the source of the accessible materials and the contribution of KIX funding across the three countries. The distribution process will include sourcing devices such as laptops, projectors to the treatment schools to enable utilisation and assessment. The procurement approach is under development as mapping of the already available devices is being conducted to enable proper support.

Table 5: Number of materials to be adapted per country.

Country	Funded by KIX	Leveraged from Partners	Total
Rwanda	7	93	100
Malawi	40	60	100
Kenya	75	25	100

The materials cover various themes, including adventure, health, the environment, critical thinking, animals, folklore, family, friendship, community, and problem-solving.

The materials are adapted to support inclusive education and are developed following the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles. The adaptation work to make them accessible is done by digitising the materials into an **EPUB** format and adding in the adaptations specified below. The specific adaptations that are used are;

- Image descriptions
- Human audio narration
- Sign Language videos
- Interactive questions
- Glossary words

Figure 3: A screenshot of a learning material that has not been adapted.

Figure 4: A screenshot showing a page from a learning material adapted by embedding sign language video.

Key learnings:

- a. It is essential to involve the organisations of persons with disabilities that oversee Deaf education in guidance and standardisation of the sign languages in respective countries. This collaboration supports the quality assurance of the materials we adapt and produce
- b. Distribution of the adapted materials requires additional accommodation for provisioning on devices such as laptops to enhance utilisation. Furthermore, a mapping of available infrastructures and devices in the schools is conducted so that we can pre-determine extra support needed for the utilisation of these adapted materials.

iii. Deaf teachers recruitment:

The sign language-rich environment is effective by having Deaf teachers in the schools to support the learning of the Deaf children. Hence, through this project, we have recruited Deaf teacher assistants who will be appointed in the treatment schools during this project. This will provide evidence on how Deaf teachers play a key role in sign language acquisition for the Deaf child. The recruited Deaf teachers per country are as follows:

- Kenya: 10 (5F+5M), that is subject to change due to the relocation of the Deaf teachers.
- Rwanda: 5 (3F+2M)
- Malawi 4 (3F+1M)

These teachers will be working alongside the already existing teachers in the treatment schools, providing support in the classes, especially around the use of sign language for improved comprehension of the lessons. They will also be in charge of training the hearing teachers on sign language for improved skills in the language used for Deaf learners. Finally, the Deaf teachers will be in charge of conducting the assessment of the Deaf learners on learning gains and periodic reporting on the utilisation of the distributed accessible learning materials.

Key results:

- a. In all three countries, there are very few Deaf teachers employed by the government in the teaching profession. This is due to the challenges that Deaf people face in accessing quality education. Through this project, we hope to advocate for the Deaf youth assistants, especially those who will be engaged in this project, to be accepted in the

teaching profession and receive official appointments.

- b. To align with best practices in early childhood development, where female teachers are predominantly encouraged to teach and support young children, our selection process purposefully recruited more female Deaf teacher assistants than males.

iv. Research Sign Language Assessment test training and piloting:

To prepare for impact assessments, we developed and contextualised the assessment tools for each country's sign language. After adapting the RSLA for each country, the Kentalis team trained the eKitabu Rwanda team to become master trainers. These master trainers then trained the Deaf teacher assistants, who went on to pilot the tests at GS Institut Filipo Smaldone in Rwanda.

In Malawi, we used a different approach. The master trainers and Deaf teacher assistants were trained together over five days, with one day dedicated to conducting an assessment at Mountain View School for the Deaf. This combined training was necessary because the Deaf teachers required more time to familiarise themselves with the content.

Since Kenya had previously worked with the RSLA tools, they joined the Malawi team for a refresher training and participated in the pilot test in June. Kenya will conduct its own piloting of the assessment tools later, before the baseline assessment in January 2026.

Table 6: Number of learners who participated in piloting RSLA.

Country	PP1	PP2	PP3	PP4
Malawi	x	4	x	12
Country	PP1	PP2	G1	G2
Rwanda	2	2	2	2

We will measure the impact of our innovation on Deaf children's learning gains by conducting a baseline assessment and an endline assessment at the close of the academic year. Since the academic calendars vary by country, the assessments will be scheduled at different times. In Rwanda and Malawi, the baseline will be conducted in September 2025 at the start of their academic year. In Kenya, it will take place in January 2026. The assessment will target Deaf students in specific grade levels:

- **Rwanda and Kenya:** PP1, PP2, G1, and G2
- **Malawi:** PP1, PP2, PP3, and PP4

The study will be conducted with two groups: a treatment group and a control group. The treatment group will receive the intervention, while the control group will not. The intervention period will last for six months, or two academic terms, as the third term is reserved for end-of-year assessments. For each grade, the intervention will consist of a specific number of lessons in the respective Sign Language, each lasting approximately 40 minutes. All teachers will receive intensive training on using the intervention from the project team. Throughout the study, teachers will be required to keep a logbook to record their observations about the intervention.

Assessment tools: For this research, the eKitabu and Kentalis teams have developed receptive tests for the RSLA to measure the learning gains of Deaf learners. The test instructions will be given in the respective sign languages: KSL, RSL, and MSL. The RSLA instruments have been reviewed for cultural appropriateness and contextualised to meet each country's needs. As a result, we now have three distinct versions of the RSLA tool, with testing items appropriate for each country.

I choose the picture that matches the signed word.

1. My teacher signs a word
2. I look for the right picture
3. I write down the number next to the right picture.

The test will be displayed on a laptop. Children will view each item and record their answers on a provided response sheet. Teachers may offer additional instructions during the practice and exercise phases, but no further assistance will be given once the actual test begins. The following areas will be tested:

- Vocabulary:
- Finger spelling
- Sentence comprehension
- Story comprehension

Before the research study commences, all teachers will receive intensive training on how to use the assessment instrument. The test developers will be responsible for scoring the children's responses.

v. Capacity building of the project consortium team:

The team has participated in various capacity-building activities, both internally and externally organised by the KIX team. Continuous learning is a key part of this project, with new knowledge and insights gained at every stage.

Internally, to improve communication with our Deaf colleagues, the project has prioritised Sign Language (SL) learning. Deaf team members have organised SL classes in each country for their hearing colleagues.

Since the project began, we've seen significant improvements in how SL is used in meetings, training, and during activities. In Kenya, the team attends weekly KSL classes and is regularly tested to measure their skill level. Similarly, in Rwanda and Malawi, the team takes occasional SL classes to communicate

more easily with their Deaf colleagues. To further support Deaf colleagues and project implementation, permanent SL interpreters have also been employed.

On programme implementation, as the lead implementers of project activities, the eKitabu team members were trained as master trainers for the PAW and RSLA tools and will also receive training on the TPD manual. These master trainers have, in turn, trained community facilitators (CFs) and Deaf teacher assistants, who will conduct the activities at a grassroots level.

Under scaling and strategy, at the start of the project, 15 members (10 female, 5 male) of the consortium team completed the Scaling course delivered by the ROSIE team. This course enabled in-depth discussions on our scaling pathways and helped us begin drafting our strategy. It also helped to refine our research designs to fit each country's context, given the different starting points of the project. The ROSIE Focal Person has also attended various training sessions organised to improve capacity in scaling and reporting.

Lastly, the KIX team has provided training on MEL activities, including data entry, reporting, and outcome mapping. Furthermore, the team is actively participating in ongoing training sessions on costing, and lessons learned are shared during internal weekly meetings.

Progress towards objective 3: Mobilise knowledge and evidence to inform, advocate for, and improve both ECCE language of instruction policies and practices in Kenya, Malawi, and Rwanda in relation to their national sign languages as first languages and languages of instruction and improve implementation of sign-language-rich learning environments for Deaf learners.

This reporting period's knowledge and evidence mobilisation activities focused on establishing the project's foundation and sharing the objectives of the Scaling Inclusive Early Learning with Deaf Children project with key stakeholders.

i. Evidence library:

In response to the identified dearth of published resources on inclusive education, Deaf education, and disability, the project has established the Evidence Library. The platform has been designed to aggregate verified and reliable materials, facilitating widespread access for diverse stakeholders. Language customisation options are available for English, Deutsch, Arabic, Hindi, French, Mandarin, Swahili, and Portuguese users. For enhanced user accessibility, the evidence library also incorporates design features that comply with Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG), catering to the needs of readers with visual impairments. Any published works from the current project will also be added to the evidence library.

During the design phase, a prototype of the [Evidence Library](#) was shared with various stakeholders in the inclusive education community to generate feedback. Some of these stakeholders included colleagues from the World Bank, UNICEF, and the Africa KIX 19 Hub.

The preliminary feedback for the evidence library was positive, highlighting its potential for education stakeholders and suggesting KIX Hub's role in its dissemination and growth. Key inquiries and suggestions focused on the visual background, ensuring all PDFs open, improving navigation for continuous scrolling, and confirming author permissions for hosted documents. Further questions addressed the future scope, the purpose of the "log in" option (access vs. upload, and who can upload), and new feature suggestions. These included a glossary with international sign language materials, offline access for documents, a bilingual approach combining sign language and written language, and resources for interactive educator training.

The feedback above has since been incorporated into the final version of the Evidence Library, which is awaiting launch during this year's 5th World Federation of the Deaf Conference 2025 in Nairobi, Kenya, next month.

ii. Engaging education stakeholders:

The project has now been launched in all three countries, with launches taking place in Rwanda in November 2024, Kenya in April, and Malawi in May 2025. During these events, relevant government institutions, key stakeholders, and partners were informed of the project's activities and objectives. The launches provided crucial insights into how the project's design aligns with national priorities and reinforced the need for providing evidence and recommendations that can inform policy changes. This ongoing stakeholder engagement is vital for understanding how to scale our innovations

successfully.

In **Kenya**, the project launch was attended by 33 participants, including government representatives from the Early Childhood Development (ECD) department and the Ministry of Education, as well as NGOs, private organisations focused on inclusive education, members of the Deaf community, and teachers from special schools for the Deaf. Key insights from the workshop focused on the following points:

1. **Early Childhood Development (ECD) Funding:** There is insufficient data to support decision-making in ECD. Furthermore, while governors have funding for ECD, they are directing it towards bursaries instead of development, resulting in minimal government support for ECD centres.
2. **Teacher Deployment:** The distribution of trained teachers is uneven, with many professionals concentrated in Nairobi rather than in underserved regions. A new TSC policy on teacher recruitment, which requires a mean grade of C, is also likely to affect the quality of new recruits.
3. **Curriculum and Policy:** While the KICD creates the curriculum and KISE adapts it for special needs, a new Ministry of Education policy on integration lacks clear guidance on emotional and social inclusivity.
4. **Kenya Sign Language (KSL) Education:** There is a significant shortage of qualified early-years teachers for KSL, as most are placed in secondary schools. This, coupled with a high student-to-teacher ratio, places a considerable strain on education delivery. There is also a major gap in developing KSL as a fully teachable language.

In Malawi, the project launch was attended by the Deputy Minister of Gender, Community Development and Social Welfare, the Honourable Halima Daudi. On behalf of the government, she reaffirmed its commitment to promoting inclusive education by ensuring Deaf children have access to sign language and pledged to equip schools with trained sign language educators. The launch, which had a total of 91 participants, also included the honorary consul of Canada, the GPE country focal person, local authorities, members of the Deaf community, and parents of Deaf children from the selected schools.

Key insights:

1. Stakeholders present at the project launch in Malawi provided recommendations on how to enhance the project design. These included: offering sign language lessons for government officials and regular teachers; involving Deaf teachers within the Ministry of Education system to support the project; and engaging with the Ministry of Health to intensify early screening and identification.
2. The support and development of Deaf education vary significantly across the three countries. Therefore, scaling the sign language-rich environment will require different approaches and pathways for each context.
3. The recognition of sign language as an official language of instruction is crucial for promoting Deaf education. In Kenya, KSL is approved and recognised as a language of instruction, whereas in Rwanda and Malawi, it has not yet received official approval.

iii. Research Advisory Committee establishment and engagement

The Research Advisory Committee (RAC) will play a critical role in providing guidance and support to the project, particularly in ensuring that the design, approach, reports, and other outputs are in line with the research objective, are appropriate to the country context, and are of a high quality and standard.

In all three countries, RAC members have been identified and selected to be part of the project. In Kenya, the RAC is made up of 6 members (3 female, 3 male) from KNAD, KISE, the Ministry of Education (Directorate of Special Needs Education department), Georgetown University, and Maseno University (Deaf Education department). In Rwanda, the RAC is made up of 5 male members representing the Rwanda Basic Education Board, the National Child Development Agency, the Rwanda National Union of the Deaf, and a university professor. In Malawi, the committee is made of 3 males and 1 female from the Ministry of Education (Department of Inclusive Education), the Ministry of Gender Community Development and Social Welfare (Department of Child Affairs), the Malawi National Association of the Deaf (MANAD), and a University of Malawi Professor who is also the RAC chairperson.

The RAC will meet quarterly to gain understanding from the implementing team on the progress status, learning, challenges and mitigation approaches, and to review reports and key outputs produced during that period. Additionally, the RAC will support the presentation of findings from the project during key convenings with various stakeholders.

Challenges and mitigation strategies

During the first half of the year, project activities focused on preparing for implementation. This involved building relationships and communicating our objectives to relevant stakeholders, including government representatives. The project was launched in each country during this phase, which enabled crucial engagement with ministries and other partners. Our collaboration with government officials has already led to successes that ensure the smooth continuation of our project plans:

- Kick-off meetings in Kenya and Malawi were attended by ministry representatives and other key stakeholders.
- The Government of Rwanda showed a strong interest in the project, providing a letter of recommendation and communicating with other relevant ministries and districts where the research will take place. Similarly, the Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Gender in Malawi have both expressed interest and assigned focal persons to support the implementation of activities.
- We have also been receiving ongoing support from the IDRC project officer, who has guided us on activity design, reviewed our project documents, and ensured that we are following all requirements and staying on track with our milestones. We have scheduled monthly check-in calls to share progress, upcoming activities, challenges, and mitigation plans. Additionally, as part of their technical support, IDRC personnel visited the team in Rwanda to ensure the coordination of KIX-funded projects in the country.

The project faced a few challenges during the first half of the year, which the team addressed with various mitigation strategies. A significant delay occurred in acquiring a research permit from Malawi, due to a government fee equivalent to 10% of the research budget that had not been foreseen. Due to the significant cost, the team initially sought a waiver in collaboration with the Ministry of Education.

However, to prevent further delays in activity implementation, the fee was eventually paid, and the permit was secured in February 2025.

The project also experienced a turnover of a key individual who served as both the MEL and ROSIE focal person and a member of the Malawi team. To mitigate this, a new MEL and ROSIE focal person was recruited. An additional MEL Manager was also hired to further strengthen the Malawi team and address the resulting gap in capacity.

A major challenge was the recruitment of qualified Deaf teachers, as the initial high requirements did not align with the educational backgrounds of the available candidates. To address this, the project applied for and received a waiver to lower the selection standards. In Malawi, the minimum qualification was lowered from the Malawi School Certificate of Education (MSCE) to the Junior Certificate of Education. In Kenya and Rwanda, the recruitment process was redesigned to focus on competency and experience rather than formal qualifications. This comprehensive approach involved credential verification, a lesson plan test, a practical classroom exercise, and a core-curriculum activities test. The process helped the team to identify each candidate's competencies and skill gaps, which was essential for designing their training programme.

Impact of USAID funding halt on our project sustainability:

The Scaling Inclusive Early Learning with Deaf Children project has no USAID funding, direct or leveraged. However, before the USAID freeze, the research team had been coordinating with other USAID-funded projects in the 3 countries that directly or indirectly involved Deaf children, their teachers, parents, and relevant government stakeholders.

In 2024, USAID awarded the Strengthening Equitable Education for the Deaf (SEED) project in **Rwanda** to focus on supporting and strengthening Deaf education. To ensure effective collaboration and avoid duplicated efforts, eKitabu and SEED colleagues held coordination meetings to share priorities, align work plans, and find ways of working together.

Key similarities between the two projects in Rwanda were:

1. Participating schools for the Deaf: The research project involves 8 ECD centres and lower primary schools for the Deaf; SEED had planned to involve 18 schools, including the 8 in the research project.
2. Distribution of accessible materials in RSL developed by eKitabu and the Rwanda National Union of the Deaf (RNUD).
3. Recruitment of Deaf teachers and teaching assistants.
4. Parents' awareness activities.

In Malawi, USAID implemented the Deaf Education Language of Instruction and Transition in Education (DELITES) project, which aimed to research challenges affecting Deaf education and provide recommendations for improvement. eKitabu was one of the leading organisations supporting this effort with data collection and analysis. This project was aligned with the KIX project, as its report would have been a valuable tool for advocating to policymakers and implementers to provide sign language-rich environments for Deaf learners.

Furthermore, USAID also had the NextGen activity, which began in 2022. One of its components focused on adapting and digitising pre-primary and primary school teaching and learning materials (TLMs) to global and accessibility standards. eKitabu had presented a scope of work to adapt these

materials and make them accessible to all learners with disabilities; however, this activity did not move forward as planned. Similarly, in Kenya, eKitabu had developed a scope of work to adapt learning materials and support teacher training on their utilisation and Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles for a USAID-funded project called the Kenya Primary Literacy Program, but this project was also not implemented.

The coordination approach planned under these different projects in the three countries was designed to enhance the sustainability of our innovation. It aimed to promote adoption by governments and other stakeholders by expanding the evidence base and reaching more learners, teachers, and parents.

- **Section 2: Project outputs, outcomes, and results**

This section details the achievements and progress against the outputs and outcome indicators outlined in the results framework. The complete results framework table can be found in the annex. The project achieved several key results for this period that align with the milestones outlined in the results framework.

Output or outcome #	Indicator #	Projected annual milestone	Actual / achieved annual milestone	Explanation of variance
Immediate outcomes				
Instances of applied research projects, ROSIE or observatory sharing research evidence through hubs	3.3.2	1	1	The situation analysis has been developed, but has not yet been shared with the KIX hub
Output				
# thematic research outputs presenting new knowledge or innovation in KIX thematic areas and/or GPE PC specific education priorities (disaggregated by KIX mechanism, type, and GEI relevance)	4.1.1	1	1	(Situational analysis report, 100% GESI related)
Secondary knowledge products tailored for a particular use (disaggregated by KIX mechanism, type and GEI relevance)	4.2.1	2	3	Only 2 blog posts have been published on the KIX news page, while the other 2 are still in the review process

Activities where KIX or other (in case of hubs) research is presented or knowledge exchange among educational stakeholders takes place (disaggregated by KIX mechanism, type, and GESI relevance)	4.2.2	3	3	ICED, World Bank conference, Africa Childcare Forum
Activities aimed at strengthening the capacity of educational stakeholders engaged in learning exchange, applied research or country support (disaggregated by KIX mechanism, type, GESI relevance)	4.3.1	4	6	PAW, project launch,

i. Event log:

Project launch events were held in Kenya on 11 April 2025 and in Malawi on 30 May 2025. These kickoff meetings brought together key stakeholders from relevant government institutions. The events successfully highlighted the project's alignment with government priorities and generated interest in the project's results and knowledge mobilisation efforts. Parents' awareness workshops were conducted in Rwanda from 9 to 11 March and in Malawi from 27 to 29 May. The workshops served to launch the community facilitator programme, establish parent peer support groups, and emphasise the importance of early intervention and language development for Deaf children.

Coordination meetings were held with government institutions in both Malawi and Rwanda. The purpose was to introduce the project design and request support in working with the selected schools. In Malawi, several meetings took place with the Ministry of Gender and the Ministry of Education, while in Rwanda, a meeting was held with the Rwanda Education Board's (REB) Deputy Director General.

The first quarterly meeting of the Research Advisory Committee (RAC) was held in Rwanda. The meeting successfully coordinated the members and gathered their input on the work plan. Subsequent quarterly meetings are planned for the next quarter.

ii. Output logs:

Two key research outputs, published as blogs, are now available on the KIX news page following the recent events.

- eKitabu joins platforms to champion collaborative and inclusive early learning from the project participation in the World Bank Conference held in Rwanda in February (<https://www.gpekix.org/news/ekitabu-joins-platform-champion-collaborative-and-inclusive-early-learning>)
- Regional initiative for inclusive sign language environments for Deaf children from the Kenya project kick-off. (<https://www.gpekix.org/news/regional-initiative-inclusive-sign-language-environments-deaf-children>)

Uptake milestones have not yet been met, as the project is still in the early stages of implementation.

iii. Mobilisation events:

1. ***World Bank's Strengthening Inclusive Education Systems Learning Exchange Workshop:*** As part of its ongoing commitment to inclusive education, eKitabu co-led a breakout session at the Strengthening Inclusive Education Systems Learning Exchange Workshop in Kigali, Rwanda. The workshop, organised by the World Bank from 10 to 14 February, brought together government officials, NGOs, and key stakeholders from Zambia, Malawi, and Rwanda. This learning exchange provided a vital platform to share insights and strategies for strengthening inclusive education systems, with a key theme emerging around the importance of data in informing policy decisions.

During the workshop, eKitabu's session focused on using assistive technology and adapted digital materials to support Deaf learners and learners with visual impairments. Discussions highlighted how accessible digital content can break down barriers to education for learners with disabilities. The conversations also emphasised how inclusive digital resources can be integrated into mainstream education systems to provide equal learning opportunities for all children.

2. ***Africa Child Care Forum:*** In March 2025, the team attended a conference in Kigali with the theme of "strengthening evidence, accelerating action". The Scaling Inclusive Early Learning project was featured, allowing the team to highlight its impact story, objectives, and future goals for inclusive early learning for Deaf children. The team also shared the design and goals of the Evidence Library, a platform created to bridge the knowledge gap in inclusive education. The conference brought together policymakers, NGOs, CSOs, researchers, childcare champions, and advocates from across different African countries to shape the future of childcare on the continent.
3. ***International Congress on the Education of the Deaf:*** The congress was held in Italy from 7 to 11 July. Organised every five years, the event attracts thousands of researchers, teachers, administrators, parents, and professionals from various fields worldwide, including psychology, medicine, audiology, linguistics, sociology, accessibility, arts, and technology. Our project was represented by our consortium member, the Kentalis team, who presented a video highlighting the project's objectives and its expected impact at the end of the 33-month programme.

iv. Outcome case:

The project has uploaded one outcome case to the KIX Mel Centre titled “Building Skills and Capacity on Sign Language and Deaf Education of Parents of Deaf Children in Kenya”.

A news item was also developed from the outcome case:

<https://www.ekitabu.com/news/momentum-parents-flock-to-paw-events-take-up-sign-language-training>

- **Synthesis of project results:**

While the project is in its early stages of refining inception and implementation plans, several key achievements have been realised in line with its objectives:

Under Objective 1: **Generating Knowledge and Evidence**, a situational analysis of the three countries revealed strong policy frameworks for Deaf education but also highlighted significant implementation and resource challenges. A cost-effectiveness framework was developed, drawing on global insights to create a calculation matrix to inform the project's scalability and strategic planning. A Gender Equality and Inclusion (GEI) Matrix was created to monitor the project's gender responsiveness and support the recruitment of female Deaf teachers. As part of the preparatory work, the project identified 34 schools serving over 1,600 Deaf learners, primarily in rural areas, to be included in the research activities.

Under Objective 2: **Strengthening the Capacity of ECCE Institutions and Families**, Parents Awareness Workshops (PAW) trained 94 parents as community facilitators, which resulted in peer-led sessions and fostered mindset change at a community level. The project is developing and contextualising 100 digital and accessible learning materials, adapted to local sign languages and guided by Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles. In support of inclusive pedagogy, 21 Deaf teacher assistants, prioritising female candidates, have been recruited across the three countries to serve as language models. The project piloted Receptive Sign Language Assessments (RSLA) in Rwanda and Malawi, using contextualised tools to measure learning gains. These tools will be used in the baseline and endline assessments. Continuous capacity-building initiatives are being carried out for project teams, including sign language training and technical workshops on scaling, monitoring and evaluation (MEL), and outcome mapping.

Under Objective 3: **Knowledge and Evidence Mobilisation**, an online Evidence Library was designed to centralise and disseminate high-quality resources on deaf and inclusive education. Project launches and stakeholder engagement events were held in all three countries, helping to align project activities with national priorities and enhance stakeholder buy-in. Research Advisory Committees (RACs) were established in each country to provide guidance and oversight, ensuring the quality and contextual relevance of the research.

Other notable insights across the different countries include:

- In Malawi, a preference for oralism over Malawi Sign Language (MSL) is evident in classrooms. However, during the piloting of the RSLA test, a positive shift was observed as Deaf learners showed stronger receptive skills when presented with MSL videos.
- There is a positive shift among parents who engaged in the workshops, as they are now championing the educational rights of their Deaf children. This is evident in WhatsApp groups, where parents themselves are sharing referral pathways to support their children's needs.

- **Section 3: Insights and Recommendations**

The project has made significant progress in laying the groundwork for evidence-based, inclusive, and scalable interventions for Deaf children's education. Continued emphasis on community engagement, Deaf leadership, data-driven refinement, and policy alignment will be critical for achieving systemic change.

To meet the project's objectives, we have developed recommendations concerning strategies, activity design, implementation, and coordination with relevant governments and stakeholders:

1. The schools targeted for evidence generation vary significantly in their resources, capacity, and approaches to supporting Deaf children. This variation is further complicated by their categorisation as special, inclusive, or mainstream schools. To enable the utilisation and adoption of our innovation and support improved learning gains, we recommend that government institutions and other stakeholders provide additional support. This includes increasing available resources to ensure the sustainability of a favourable environment for Deaf children. We also recommend an extensive mapping of ICT infrastructure in schools, followed by the provision of necessary devices and support to ensure the effective utilisation of the adapted content distributed during project implementation.
2. Specific activities need to be designed to advocate for the formal recognition of Rwanda Sign Language (RSL) and Malawi Sign Language (MSL) as official languages of instruction, following the precedent set by Kenya's KSL. This will be accomplished through various advocacy activities, which will be led by Organisations of Persons with Disabilities (OPDs) themselves.
3. The situational analysis identified a clear gap in the number of qualified Deaf teachers in the system. To address this, our project will support Deaf teacher assistants to enrol in teacher training colleges for certification, ensuring a sustainable workforce of qualified Deaf educators. Additionally, we will promote female representation by prioritising recruitment and leadership roles for female Deaf educators and colleagues.
4. Inclusive education for Deaf children and the engagement of their parents require a holistic support system to address critical issues such as access to information on sexual reproductive health rights (SRHR) and gender-based violence (GBV). These areas are essential to the intervention and require properly designed pathways and activities. Integrating these topics will necessitate collaboration with existing initiatives and other stakeholders. However, doing so may incur additional timelines and budget, potentially exceeding the project's threshold and requiring coordination to leverage existing resources.
5. We recommend engaging ministries and local governments early and continuously to secure buy-in, which is essential for adapting the innovation and training programmes. It is also important to continue collaborating with organisations such as OPDs, the World Bank, and other projects in inclusive education to facilitate resource sharing and harmonise efforts.

Recommendations of the project to the IDRC include:

1. The project is being implemented over a short period, but the uptake and actual impact of the innovation will require a longer timeline, particularly given the varying school calendars. We

recommend that IDRC design phasing-out activities and plan for continuous data collection beyond the project timeline to fully capture the innovation's long-term effects.

2. The current project focuses on adapting only supplementary readers into local sign languages across the three countries, which means curriculum materials will be left out. We recommend that IDRC fund the adaptation of curriculum books into local sign language, as Deaf learners require accessible materials to thrive academically and socially.
3. We recommend that IDRC fund long-term Monitoring, Evaluation and Learning (MEL). As scaling requires time, a robust MEL system is essential for measuring the long-term impact of this innovation on learners' outcomes, teacher effectiveness, and community attitudes.

Annexes:

1. Links to output

- a. eKitabu joins platforms to champion collaborative and inclusive early learning from the project participation in the World Bank Conference held in Rwanda in February (<https://www.gpekix.org/news/ekitabu-joins-platform-champion-collaborative-and-inclusive-early-learning>)
- b. Regional initiative for inclusive sign language environments for Deaf children from the Kenya project kick off. (<https://www.gpekix.org/news/regional-initiative-inclusive-sign-language-environments-deaf-children>)
- c. Research Advisory Committee meeting in Rwanda: (<https://www.gpekix.org/news/rwanda-establishes-research-advisory-committee-inclusive-early-learning-project>)
- d. Parents awareness workshops transform support deaf learners across East Africa: (<https://www.gpekix.org/news/parent-awareness-workshops-transform-support-deaf-learners-across-east-africa>)

2. Outcome case:

Building skills and capacity on sign language and Deaf education of parents of Deaf children in Kenya

Hundreds of parents have benefited from Parents Awareness Workshops held in various schools for the Deaf across the country this year. The aim of the workshops was to empower parents and guardians of learners with disabilities, especially those in schools for the Deaf, with knowledge, tools, and networks for better support at home and school.

The latest such workshop was held on 2 May at St Anthony School for the Deaf in Webuye County, Kenya and built on the momentum of the inaugural session held in November 2024. During the mid-term break in February, up to 308 parents were trained in seven different institutions, with parents inducting others in their schools. The schools included Kuja, Kambui, Kaaga, and Tumutumu schools for the Deaf. Others were St Anthony, Kedowa and Ngala schools for the Deaf. Parents at the latter two schools also received further induction during the April holiday.

Since the first PAW in Kenya, significant progress has been made, particularly in parent engagement and support structures. Two main communication channels have been put in place: WhatsApp groups to facilitate ongoing dialogue, resource sharing, and coordination; and individual phone calls to ensure parents receive personalised support and follow-ups.

Progress

Many parents who attended the first PAW in November 2024 have taken an active role in their communities. Notable progress includes greater interest in learning sign language, with more parents enrolling in Kenya Sign Language (KSL) courses to better communicate with their children.

Additionally, some parents have created informal support groups to meet regularly and learn together. “I take this opportunity to thank the eKitabu team. The three days at the Parents Awareness Workshop helped me get this far. I am now at KISE studying KSL,” said Jacky, a parent at Kedowa School for the Deaf.

Serah Wanjiru, a parent at Tumutumu School for the Deaf, was equally elated. “The experience is awesome. Parents are ready to learn. We also had a session with an officer from the National Council for Persons with Disabilities, which was very informative.”

The experience of the two parents was replicated in other schools across the country. With consistent engagement, more parents are learning KSL, advocating for disability rights, and forming support networks. Continued collaboration among schools, organisations like eKitabu, and government agencies will be key in scaling this impact.

Jackline (on the right), a parent at Kedowa School For The Deaf, attending KSL lessons in KISE, Nakuru County.

Serah, a parent at Tumutumu School for the Deaf, during a parents’ meeting.

Parents at Kedowa School for the Deaf are following proceedings.

Parents of Ngala School for the Deaf during the KSL session.

Parents and teachers of St. Anthony School for the Deaf after the training.

3. Situational analysis
4. Results framework
5. Teacher Professional Development manual